

ISic4339

I.Sicily inscription 4339

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Ragusa

Provenance

contrada Cisternazzi, from a hypogeum

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Kamarina, Museo Archeologico
Regionale di Kamarina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Di Stefano, G., Rizzone, V.G. 2012-2013. Miscellanea epigrafica iblea. *Seia*. 17-18: 49-70. At 58 no.4 fig.7

Di Stefano, G. 2013. Kamarina. Le acquisizioni, il museo tematico, la collezione "Biagio Pace", il lapidario. Ispica. At 34 ph

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